

Online Consumer Shopping Behaviour

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Introduction

Though the practice of buying from a shop personally taking time to choose and purchase in a traditional manner is common, the comfort of online shopping renders an emerging trend among consumers, especially the Gen Y. They feel online shopping saves crucial time as well as their expected products or services are available at their door step with cheaper prices compared to offline shops in lesser time. Due to this transformation in buying activity in the current era business transactions are becoming easy with the online network with much more quickness and transparency scope for digital shopping has growing extensively across the globe.

It has been evident that there have been significant changes occurring in consumer behavioral attitudes. There is a shift in the attitude of consumers drastically and eventually they are changing attitudes of lifestyle, recreation and entertainment expenditures. Market is filled with an explosion of choices of similar products, which are often not even perceptible to consumers which results in difficulty or confusion in choosing a product for consumers. Hence marketers are gauging the consumers and making strategies by effectively identifying their expectations from products, brand, and level of satisfaction.

Conceptualization of Online Shopping

The concept of online shopping started with the launch of the World Wide Web. Online shopping was invented and pioneered by Michael Aldrich in UK 1979. Charles Staks was the first person to create an online book store in 1992. Today due to the vast use of the internet in India the online shopping is increasing widely. Digital buyers in India are likely to increase by 121 million by the end of 2019 and drastically by 220 million by 2025. The average expense on digital expenses by consumers in India was 224 US dollars per the survey done in 2017.

Online Shopping Consumer Behavior

Online shopping consumer attitude or internet shopping nature refers to the process of purchasing products or services via the internet. The invention of the digital media has contrived a paradigm shift in the traditional way the people shop. Now a customer can become active virtually any time and place and purchase products or services.

The internet is a new medium at communication and number of internet users is increasing which also signifies that online purchasing is rising (Jaines, L. J., W.C, and Scheufele A.D., 2003)

In the online shopping process, potential customers recognize the need for service or merchandise when they go to the internet for information relating to that service or merchandise while searching, and are attracted by a variety of products which fulfill their needs. Then they evaluate and compare the products and choose the best one. Finally, the transaction is completed and post-sales services are provided to them. (Liang and Lai, 2000)

Emergence of E- Market

E-marketing (marketing of products and services on electronic media) The exponential growth and proliferation of digital media technologies have revolutionized as a new tool in the global market place and engendered new business models and value propositions along with e-commerce (Ahmed, 2015) and (Velasquez, 2009). E-platform is meant for creative use of digital technologies to create appealing advertisements, forms, e-shop where products can be seen, promoted through various modes along with product display, product negotiation, 3- D product view, basket selection, checkout and payment (Hooda Sanjay and Aggarwal Sandeep, 2012).

7 C's of E-Marketing

Contract: The marketers' first goal is to communicate a core promise to target customers of delivering value.

Content: Content refers to items that appear on the website. If this is clear, it increases both; price and transaction.

Construction: The promise made by e-marketers must be an interactive function that gives consumers a seamless experience. A feature like one-click ordering and automated shopping deliver the promise of convenience.

Community: Through site to user and user to user forms of interactivity, e-marketers can develop a core of dedicated customers who become avid marketers' sites too.

Concentration: Advertisers have known for some time that behavioral targeting is superior to simple demographic targeting. Consumer's past experiences help advertisers to target an advertisement much more effectively.

Convergence: The internet will become more wireless video/data/voice appliances will converge, Inland products, trade and industry along with promotional strategies will become even more international and users can find out more information or order the product right here.

Commerce: To be booming on the digital network, e-marketers will have to do more than reproduce their offline business models online. It is possible for techno marketers to be profitable even at lower sales volume if they exploit efficiencies and synergies with the offline business.

Review of Literature

Online shopping has been rising significantly from the last 15 years. Now companies are heavily investing in promotion through the internet.

Bellman, S. Lohse, G.L. & Johnson, E.J. (1999) explains that consumers worldwide can shop online 24*7. Some market sectors along with insurance, financial service, computer hardware and

software, travel, books, music, are expecting rapid growth in digital sales. Authors explain that web consumers lead a wired lifestyle as they shop online to save time.

Miyazaki D. Anthony and Fernandez Ana (2001) finds that government, industry and organizations have declared information, privacy and securities are main obstacles in online shopping and also have recognized it as an issue for both new and experienced users.

Chung W and Paynter J (2002) explained that consumers are concerned about privacy issue and it is limiting their use of internet. It is an issue which a company cannot ignore. A website with a privacy statement tells the consumers that their privacy right is identified and that the success of the online business depends on the trust of the consumers.

Cheung Christy M K and Lee Mathew K O (2006) have done extensive work and have focused on perceived trustworthiness, legal framework and third party recognition which are the determinants of consumer trust in the internet.

Zhou Lina, Dai Liwei and Zhang (2007) reveal that since 1990, online shopping has taken off as a number of consumers have started purchasing online. They have identified different factors that have an impact on their behavior such as demographic factors, internet experience, normative belief, shopping orientation, shopping motivation, personal traits, online involvement, psychological perception, and online shopping experience.

Global Scenario

Largest continent Asia along with its Pacific belt is dominating the rise of digital market as collate to the most advanced markets such as United States, United Kingdom, Japan and European regions. Especially Asian countries have forwarding more, especially in China. In the year 2016, they have transacted about \$1 trillion in digital transactions and majority came from China which is about \$899 billion (e-Marketer, 2016) worldwide retail E-commerce sales will reach \$1.915 trillion this year. Retrieved May 14, 2018.

China has the highest per country usage in the world nearly twice as large as the US. Chinese internet users are less involved in e-tailing activities such as online shopping and payment, compared to their use of the internet as a tool for entertainment, communication, and information. Although Chinese consumers perceive online shopping to be more complex, they exhibit more favorable perceptions about the relative advantages of online shopping are less concerned about the risks associated with online shopping, when compared to their American counterparts. Chinese consumers are significantly more likely to agree that online shopping is convenient, time as well as money-saving.

Objectives of the Study

1. To check the age group of consumers who use maximum online shopping.
2. To know the occupation of consumers who use more online shopping.
3. To ascertain the income level of online shoppers.
4. To check the frequency of online purchases by the individual shoppers.
5. To know the sources from where online shoppers obtain information about the online shopping apps and products.
6. To evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of online shopping.

Advantages of Online Shopping

Consumers in today's era need not depend on physical shopping which is time taking and a lengthy process. Instead they can order the things required through various online websites that can cater their needs.

Following are the Advantages of Online Shopping

1. **Saves Time:** By just clicking a button, customers can log into the website of a retail store from their computer or mobile to start shopping. They can even shop from many suppliers together which saves their time.
2. **Saves Transportation Expenses:** Online shopping is not associated with any transportation expenses. The customers can simply order what they want from. All the products that they order would be delivered to their doorstep as well. Therefore, the customers will get the opportunity to avoid transportation expenses.
3. **Shop at Any Time:** Most of the stores are open only during the daytime. Due to the hectic schedule of many customers and owing to their other personal commitments, if they are unable to shop by going to a store, they can think of shopping online for their necessities at any convenient time.
4. **Better Prices:** Products available in online stores generally tend to be cheaper when compared to the physical stores. On the other hand, the customers are offered with some exciting opportunities to save money as well. For example, one can benefit from the Great Indian Festival Deals, Big Billion Days Deals and save money on what they shop. The customers will never be able to get such amazing discounts from physical stores.
5. **No Need to line up:** The customers would never like to spend their precious time while standing on queues. Unfortunately, it would not be possible for them to avoid long line while they are shopping for what they want in offline stores. But long standing can be avoided when they go online. The customers need to add what they want to buy into the cart and directly proceed towards the checkout.
6. **Avoiding Crowds:** Crowded stores never create a pleasant experience for the customers. Therefore, they avoid shopping in crowded stores to the maximum extent and prefer online shopping stores to shop. When customers are shopping online, they would never have to deal with the frustration in crowded stores. Therefore, shopping would become a smoother experience.
7. **Quick Search for What One Wants:** Customers can easily search for the items that they require by using filters as per their convenience. Therefore, one can quickly shop for what they want.
8. **More variety:** The choices online are amazing. One can find almost any brand or item they are looking for. Customers can get in on the latest international trends without spending money on airfare. They can shop from retailers in other parts of the state, country, or even world instead of being limited to their own geographical boundary. They can also select from different varieties, size and color.
9. **Can send gifts more easily:** Sending gifts to known people along with attractive packing and gift wrapping can be done through online purchases.
10. **Effective price comparability:** Searching and comparing the products and their prices are much easy if done through online. If the customers are shopping for appliances, for example, through the existing consumer reviews and product comparisons customers can research firsthand experience, ratings, and reviews for most products and retailers.

Limitations of Digital Shopping

1. **Contradictory Impact of Heavy Packaging:** Packing the goods in several layers of plastic and cardboard packaging is not safe for the environment and society.
2. **Delay in Shipping the Products:** Even the best and largest shipping companies and suppliers cannot assure the time of delivery. Many a times items get lost, detoured, damaged, or delivered to the wrong address more often.

3. **Risk of Extortion:** Digital shopping may lead to greater risk of misrepresentation such as credit card hosing, unethical hacking, identity theft, counterfeit products, dummy websites that are plenty.
4. **Addiction to Digital Media:** Shopping online can turn into a marathon of scrolling and clicking down rabbit holes for most of the day.
5. **Contact with Community:** If all the business is done through online, there will be no human connection or social interaction with the community and a person may become mentally unfit.
6. **Display Piece may not with the Actual Delivery:** Online shopper cannot identify the quality, and durability just by looking at an item displayed in the website. Products that look attractive may not be the same when the customer actually receives it.
7. **Returning the unwanted Products can be Complicated:** Some sellers make the process lengthy which makes the customer return the merchandise or get a refund.
8. **Unfriendly and Complicated Websites:** Some sites require that the consumer join their mailing list and make it impossible to unsubscribe. And customer can't figure out how to purchase or return an item or speak to customer service.

Pros and Cons of Shopping Online

Advantages of Digital purchases	Disadvantages of Shopping Online
Comfort & Convenience	Negative Environmental Impact of Packaging material thrown.
Cheaper Prices	Shipping Delays
More Variety & Sizes	Risk of cheating
Easy to Send Gifts	Less Contact With Your Community
More Control	Spending Too Much Time Online
Easy Price Comparisons	Returns Can Be Complicated
No Crowds	Consumer do not Know What they are Getting
No Sales Pressure	Unfriendly, and Complicated Websites

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Primary data is identified for the research work. The required information is obtained from 100 respondents by administering the questionnaire.

Through the available data, interpretation has been done as follows:

Age of Respondents

Occupation of Respondents

Income of the Respondents

Frequency of Shopping

Sources of Information

Findings

1. As per the analysis, 30% of the male respondents who are of the age between 26-30 years and 35% of the female respondents between the age group of 31-35 years have more access to internet shopping. The rest of the respondents belong to different age groups and are scattered.
2. The habit of online shopping is more for the students (about 47%). The rest who frequently shop through online are housewives (13%) and businessmen (12%).
3. Respondents who have income level up to Rs.10,000 buy more digitally, which is around 53%. Only 16% of the respondents with income level of Rs.30,000 shop online.
4. More than half of the consumers obtain information about the products through advertisements on the websites. The least of the people will get the information from their known circle.

Conclusion

The prevalence of online shopping has raised the interest of retailers to focus on this area with more and more consumers opting for digital media for their purchases.

The introduction of personal computers and the internet has changed the way of living of people not only for the communication process but also for the assimilation of information. The internet is considered as the major construct of the commercial landscape with the increasing popularity of online shopping or social media purchase habits.

But on the other hand, cybercrime issues are increasing and it results in data breach as well as cyber attacks and it's a caution for the online shoppers not to share any of their private data as well as financial information.

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